

Study on semiconductor material silicon for photovoltaic application using hot wire chemical vapor deposition techniques

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Abstract

Large grain polycrystalline silicon thin film on low cost and robust substrate is an interesting area of research for photovoltaic devices. This film can be used to fabricate solar cell which has a potential to achieve 20% efficiency like multi crystalline silicon solar cell with the advantage of thin film fabrication techniques. In this thesis we have investigated the possibility of growing large grain (220) oriented poly crystalline silicon films, 2 to 3 micron thick, from silane-hydrogen mixture, by hot wire chemical vapour deposition (HWCVD). Several substrates i) Si/SiO₂, ii) TiO₂ layer on glass, iii) textured nickel-5% tungsten metal strip, iv) crystalline sapphire and v) alkali free borosilicate glass have been used in this work.

The growth of intrinsic poly crystalline silicon film was performed starting with a thin nucleation layer at 400°C followed by the thickening stage at 600°C with higher silane concentration. We have optimized the growth conditions and one micron of well passivated hydrogenated (220) oriented polycrystalline film were grown successfully. We have used several characterization techniques for the evaluation of the optical, topographical and electrical properties of the film.

The growth of boron doped poly crystalline and amorphous silicon film was also performed following by process similar to that used for intrinsic poly silicon film using HWCVD with the addition of diborane to the gas mixture for boron doping the silicon.

The HWCVD system used for the synthesis of intrinsic and p-type polycrystalline silicon films did not have provision for n-type doping. For synthesis of phosphorous doped n-type silicon film, we initially explored doping intrinsic polycrystalline silicon film by using two different sources of phosphorous followed by Laser annealing. One approach used i) spin-on phosphorous dopant film about one micron thick and the other approach used ii) phosphorous ion implantation.

For both these approaches, we have investigated the possibility of dopant activation by irradiation with infrared continuous wave laser which can uniformly scan the sample along X-Y directions. Laser annealing is performed varying the laser power and scan speed to ensure suitable laser annealing condition. Sheet resistivity measurement was carried out to verify the laser annealing process. In this case the several characterization techniques were also followed for the evaluation of the optical, topographical and electrical properties of the film. However, the n-type silicon films synthesised in this manner were not device quality. At

this stage, we got access to another HWCVD reactor equipped with synthesis of n-type silicon using phosphine as the dopant gas.

After the above growth experiments, we took initiative to stack all these silicon layers in order to apply them in photovoltaic application. In this case we have fabricated an n-i-p structure on glass using two different HWCVD systems, starting with synthesis n-type silicon on glass in one reactor. This was transferred to the second HWCVD reactor for the synthesis of intrinsic polycrystalline silicon film. After this, a combination of a thin layer of amorphous intrinsic silicon followed by p-type amorphous silicon film was deposited to form a hetero junction between the intrinsic polycrystalline silicon and p-type amorphous silicon layer. The structure is well known as heterojunction with intrinsic thin layer (HIT). In our case the intrinsic polycrystalline silicon layer acts as the light absorber layer, the top p-type amorphous silicon acts as emitter layer, while the bottom n-type silicon acts as back surface field. The performance of the device was evaluated from dark and illuminated I-V characterization. It was observed that the light response was very weak. Further work is necessary to improve the photovoltaic action. For this, we have to increase the thickness and material quality of the light absorbing layer, and improve the quality of junctions.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Photovoltaic (PV) technology

1.1.1 Past and present

The study of photovoltaic (PV) effect began in 1839 when Edmund Becquerel discovered an increment in current of an electrolyte cell when exposed to light [1]. Photovoltaic effect in solid state was discovered first in selenium while investigating photoconductivity and attributed to energy barrier to current flow at metal semiconductor junction. The modern PV era began in 1953 at Bell laboratories where scientists Gerald Pearson, Daryl Chapin and Calvin Fuller fabricated the first solar cell using p-n junction in silicon [2]. As the cost of commercial solar cell was as high as 300USD per watt, it was not practical for mass production; however it proved useful for powering satellites proposed by Gordon Raisbeck one of Daryl Chapin's colleague in 1955 [3]. Despite the initial concern of photovoltaic's future, research continued and cost reduced to 100USD per watt by the year 1970 which was mainly used for powering satellites [4]. At present the production cost has reduced to 1 USD per watt peak for solar modules ($\geq 125\text{W}$) made of multi crystalline silicon [5]. Thus the number of terrestrial solar power units has increased dramatically in various fields of necessity such as signalling, communication and remote sensing, and even powering the water pumps in agricultural fields to the use of solar PV as energy source alternative to fossil fuels. Now a days about large percentage of the terrestrial photovoltaic solar cells are made of silicon [5].

With the reduction in production cost, the conversion efficiency becomes a real concern to the scientist. Mono crystalline silicon solar cell reached an efficiency of 24.5 % by University of New South Wales [6], commercial mono crystalline manufactured by SunPower achieved an efficiency of 20.4% [7]. Large grain polycrystalline silicon produced cheaply

compared to mono crystalline silicon can have the properties close to mono crystalline silicon [8]. Commercial thick film polycrystalline silicon solar cell reached 17.7% efficiency manufactured by Kyocera [9]. Details about the efficiency of solar cells and modules are discussed in this chapter in the section 1.1.4.

1.1.2 Materials for Photovoltaics

Since only photons with energies above the band gap of a semiconductor are absorbed, the band gap of the material used for a photovoltaic device must be engineered in order to produce the maximum power for a given illumination, given that the solar spectrum as a function of photon energy under one sun condition [10,11]. Semiconductors with larger band gaps produce higher photovoltages, but absorb and convert fewer of the incident photons, resulting in lower currents. Semiconductors with smaller band gaps absorb most of the solar radiation, but convert most of the energy to heat. A balanced condition for the solar cell with the best efficiency is to use material with band gap near the peak of the solar spectrum, between 1 and 2 eV [12]. Compound semiconductors GaAs, GaInP, InP, CdTe, and CIS (copper indium diselenide), and indirect band gap materials, like silicon, are used in the fabrication of solar cells. Both amorphous and crystalline (polycrystalline and monocrystalline) silicon are used in the manufacture of photovoltaic devices. However, amorphous silicon suffers from the Staebler-Wronski effect [13], in which dangling bonds are created under illumination, causing the efficiency to degrade. Research communities turn then to crystalline silicon technology, which is capable of providing efficiencies greater than 20% [14].

1.1.3 Poly crystalline silicon technology

One of the most promising technologies for reduced cost photovoltaic technology involves the growth of thin film polycrystalline silicon on foreign substrates. Although the efficiencies of thin-film polycrystalline solar cells are lower than those of crystalline silicon cells, production costs are significantly lower. In 1996 Astropower Corporation produced the first commercially available polycrystalline silicon thin-film modules using a high-temperature process on a foreign substrate [15]. Laboratory solar cell with an active layer of 50 μm thick was fabricated on a foreign substrate achieved an efficiency of 16.6% [16]. Fabrication of the polycrystalline silicon thin film on glass for photovoltaic application could

be an innovative technology that combines the robustness of crystalline silicon wafer based technology with the advantage of thin film [17].

1.1.4 Efficiency of silicon solar cell

Since January 1993, Progress in Photovoltaics has published six monthly listings of the highest confirmed efficiencies for a range of photovoltaic cell and module technologies [18,19,20]. Here we have mentioned the results up to 2014 published in the solar cell efficiency table (version 44) [21]. Crystalline silicon on glass (CSG) solar cell achieved an efficiency of 10.5 % shown in table 1.1.

Table 1.1 Highest confirmed terrestrial solar cell efficiency measured under AM1.5 spectrum [21]

Classification of solar cell	Efficiency (%)	Description	References
Silicon (Crystalline)	25.6±0.5	Panasonic (HIT structure)	[22]
Silicon (Multi crystalline)	20.4±0.5	FhG-ISE	[23]
Silicon (amorphous)	10.1±0.3	Oerlikon Solar Lab, Neuchatel	[24]
Silicon (Micro crystalline)	11.0±0.3	AIST	[25]
Si (large multi crystalline)	19.5 ± 0.4	Q-Cells, laser-fired contacts	[26]
III-V GaAs Thin film	28.8±0.9	Alta device	[27]
CIGS thin film cell	20.5±0.6	Solibro, on glass	[28]
Dye sensitised cell	11.9±0.4	Sharp	[29]
Silicon (mini module)	10.5±0.3	CSG solar (<2µm on glass, 20 cells)	[30]

1.1.5 Technology of growth of PV material

Growth technology of solar cell material has improved significantly. Several low-temperature deposition methods for polycrystalline silicon have been studied, including the most widely used plasma enhanced chemical vapour deposition (PECVD) [31], very high frequency glow discharge (VHF-GD) [32], Electron Cyclotron Resonance CVD (ECR-CVD) [33] and Hot-Wire CVD (HWCVD) [34] which is the focus of our study. Furthermore, these kind of materials can also be synthesized by other techniques like rapid thermal annealing (RTA) [35], laser melt re-crystallisation (LMR) [36] and aluminium induced crystallisation [37].

1.2 Future of Photovoltaics with silicon

1.2.1 Heterojunction with intrinsic thin (HIT) layer solar cell

Hetero junction with intrinsic thin layer (HIT) silicon solar cells have reached photovoltaic efficiencies in excess of 22% reported by Sanyo Corp. Japan whereas world highest efficiency 25.6% reported by Panasonic shown in table 1.1. The Sanyo solar cell consists of a mono crystalline silicon (c-Si) wafer with thin layers of doped and undoped hydrogenated amorphous silicon (aSi:H) to form the junction. In the Sanyo HIT solar cell [38], an intrinsic thin layer is deposited between the wafer and the doped amorphous layer as back-surface field (BSF). For many years, and still as ongoing research, the optimisation of these structures has concentrated on the properties of the interface between the front amorphous hydrogenated silicon (a-Si:H) layers and the crystalline silicon (c-Si) wafer by plasma enhanced chemical vapour deposition (PECVD).

In addition, the back-contact properties have been investigated and improved. Because of the effect of the interface defects on the device properties, characterisation techniques are required not only for the fully processed cells but for the wafer structures with various deposited amorphous silicon layers. Recent research activities have in common that the characterisation of the passivated wafers has contributed to the solar cell optimisation. A summary of the results of the German project on both n and p type wafers can be found in [39]. In the French network [40] alternative thin layers of polymorphous silicon have been deposited to optimise the hetero junction cells, also in view of industrial processes. The focus of the hetero junction research at National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) [41] is on alternative deposition techniques like hot-wire chemical vapour

deposition for the amorphous layers. In Neuchatel, very-high frequency PECVD has been applied to process hetero junction solar cells with high open-circuit voltages [42].

1.2.2 Application of Lasers in polycrystalline solar cell fabrication

Fabrication of polycrystalline silicon thin-film involves high-temperature processing such as crystallization, dopant diffusion and activation, and defect annealing. These processes require temperatures of more than 1000°C [43,44]. Poly-Si material is thermally stable and its electronic quality benefits from high temperature treatments. However, choosing glass as a substrate as low cost material cannot withstand high temperature for sufficiently long period. In this case lasers can deliver power sufficient to heat silicon films up to melting point while laser scanning speeds allow control of the exposure duration in the milliseconds range (1–100ms). In this range, the heat transfer is mostly confined to a thin film of few microns [45,46]. As a result, we can apply higher temperatures to silicon film while keeping the glass at a far lower temperature [47,48].

During the past few years we have seen an extensive use of rapid thermal processing (RTP) by means of halogen lamps on polycrystalline silicon materials to reduce the point defects present in the poly-Si layers and to activate the dopant elements [49,50,51,52]. However this method fails to achieve temperatures above 950°C for long time (>1 min) while keeping the borosilicate glass substrate intact. Using laser thermal annealing (LTA), it is possible to achieve very high temperature very close to the melting point of crystalline silicon for few seconds with minimal or negligible deformation of borosilicate glass substrate [53].

Lasers are being used for fabricating passivated emitter rear cell (PERC) solar cells of silicon. In this structure, instead of the regular silicon Al BSF cell where Al paste is screen printed directly on the back of the cell, in PERC cell one first deposits silicon nitride (SiN), drills holes in SiN by using a laser and then deposits Al. This cell has reached 20% efficiency [54].

In our study, we have used infrared lasers for the following processes, i) damage annealing and dopant activation in poly crystalline silicon layer implanted with phosphorous, ii) dopant diffusion into undoped poly crystalline silicon layer using spin-on dopant film, and iii) laser-induced liquid-phase crystallization of 100nm thin n-type silicon films to be used as a back surface field of n-i-p structure device.

1.2.3 Glass substrate for polycrystalline silicon solar cell

Thin-film technologies allow one to separate the electrically active and mechanically supportive material by depositing the active silicon thin film onto a low-cost substrate by means of several deposition processes mentioned in section 1.1.5. With this technology, the greatest reduction in cost is due to the reduction in silicon. Half of the costs associated with the traditional crystalline silicon solar cells, is due to the silicon wafer itself [54]. Scrap silicon from the semiconductor industry, the main source of silicon for the photovoltaic industry up until a few years ago, was available for \$25/kg in 2003. But with demand increasing, the photovoltaic industry now pays for non-scrap silicon at \$50/kg [55]. By depositing a thin-film of silicon on a low-cost substrate, one can decrease the material cost even further, and perhaps even take advantage of this step by depositing on building materials, such as window glass, roof top steel shed, to decrease installation and material costs.

There are several strategies to pursuing crystalline Si thin-films on glass substrates. One involves the crystallization of the entire amorphous silicon device by metal induced crystallization. With this technique, the metal reduces the energy and temperature necessary to crystallize the film. This method has been commercialized by crystalline silicon on glass (CSG) Solar cell production shown in Table 1.1. They have achieved small module efficiencies of 10.4 % for a 95 cm² module.

1.3 Review of Literature: HWCVD

1.3.1 HWCVD deposited solar cell

The low hydrogen content of device-quality hot wire-deposited amorphous silicon films makes them useful for inclusion in photovoltaics. In 1998, Bauer et al. at the University of Kaiserslautern recorded an initial efficiency of 10.4% using a p-i-n structure on a glass substrate with the i-layer deposited by HWCVD at low-temperature, although these cells degraded by approximately 30% when exposed to light [56]. In 2000, Kaiserslautern reported 8.0% efficiency using hot wire deposited p and n type layers on ITO-coated glass [57]. Nelson et al. at NREL have reported initial efficiencies of 5.7% with i-layers deposited at growth rates of 130°A/s [58]. Microcrystalline silicon deposited by HWCVD has also shown promise as a material for solar cells. Meier et al. [59] at the University of Neuchatel have obtained 12% efficiency from a “micromorph” cell using tandem $\mu\text{c-Si:H-a-Si:H}$ cells on ITO-coated glass substrates. The total device thickness is only 1.1 μm . Nikura et al. at Ecole Poly

technique report a 4.6% efficient cell with an n-i-p structure and a 2 μ m thick i-layer grown at 300°C [60]. Rath et al. have fabricated an HWCVD n-i-p cell with 3% efficiency [61].

1.3.2 Recent work using HWCVD

Most recent results of scientific research and process developments as well as new applications in the field of hot-wire activated chemical vapour deposition (HWCVD) are presented in the international HWCVD conference, held in October, 2014, Germany hosted by Fraunhofer Institute for Surface Engineering and Thin Films (IST) [62]. The recent research using HWCVD techniques are summarised as below. Industrialization of HWCVD for thin film application [63], low temperature impurity doping [64], deposition of low temperature SiO₂ film [65], n-type crystalline silicon hetero junction solar cell [66], polycrystalline silicon thin film with hydrogen for photovoltaic application [67], material development in solar energy research [68] and single junction solar cell on nano imprinted paper [69] are the most recent research related to silicon film technology for photovoltaic applications. Thus HWCVD provides a huge opportunity for the researchers to develop low cost and robust material for thin film as well as photovoltaic applications.

1.4 Objectives

The objective of this work is to explore the possibilities of HWCVD process for the growth of polycrystalline silicon films for photovoltaic application on a cheap amorphous substrate such as glass. We therefore optimized a multi chamber HWCVD system for the growth process of intrinsic silicon film. Next, we investigate the possibilities of growing boron doped polycrystalline and amorphous silicon film along with phosphorous doped microcrystalline silicon film using HWCVD system for photovoltaic application. Further, the objective of this work is to establish a basic framework for a device quality n-i-p structure once the optimizations of individual layers are performed.

1.5 Outlook of the thesis

This thesis is organized first with a brief introduction into the photovoltaics history, its market potential, the route for thin-film silicon solar cells, and the current status of large-grained polycrystalline film in photovoltaic industry. Future of silicon solar cell technology using hetero junction with intrinsic thin layer, laser annealing for defect passivation and silicon on low cost substrate are also discussed in brief.

Chapter 2 is a summary of hot-wire chemical vapour deposition (HWCVD) instrument setup, including the growth condition optimization for the silicon film using HWCVD. Advantages and disadvantages of using this technique are also discussed. Chapter 3 is a summary of theory and instrumentation techniques of characterization tools.

We can divide the thesis into four main chapters, covering growth and characterization of i) Intrinsic film in chapter 4, ii) boron doped p-type silicon film in chapter 5, iii) n-type silicon film in chapter 6 and iv) n-i-p diode structure in chapter 7. Chapter 4 follows with the synthesis of intrinsic large grain poly crystalline silicon film under hydrogen dilution on different substrate such as glass, nickel, titanium dioxide coated glass etc.

The characterization of the silicon films are then discussed by looking at the unique surface morphology, structural evolution, optical spectral response, electrical analysis and crystalline orientation of these films. Chapter 5 covers the synthesis of p-type boron doped silicon film followed by morphological, structural, electrical and optical characterization. Chapter 6 covers the synthesis of n-type phosphorous doped silicon thin film on glass substrate. In this chapter we have introduced three different source of phosphorous. Laser irradiation for dopant activation and defect annealing also implemented including detailed characterization of these films. Chapter 7 discusses the fabrication of n-i-p device structure using HWCVD followed by electrical results analysis of the device. Future research directions that would take advantage of the unique film morphologies and structures, along with a brief conclusion of this thesis are in Chapter 8. In the appendix part we have given the necessary images of fabrication and characterization tool. Detail steps and procedure of substrate cleaning, chemical etching of silicon, mask plate cleaning are discussed. In an extended part we have also given the detail route for preparation of silicon sample for cross section transmission electron microscope imaging.

Chapter 2

Hot Wire Chemical Vapour Deposition

2.1 Introduction

In this chapter we have described the mechanism and operation of the catalytic hot wire chemical vapour deposition (HWCVD) cluster instrument used for the synthesis of polycrystalline, amorphous and microcrystalline silicon films. In our study we have used two separate HWCVD systems. For all samples, intrinsic poly crystalline silicon film and p-type amorphous silicon film synthesis is performed in a three chamber instrument. This system does not have provision for synthesis of n type doped silicon film. N-type microcrystalline silicon film synthesis performed in a separate four chamber instrument. Details of these two systems are discussed in Appendix I.

We have also conducted a brief study on substrate temperature using in situ thermocouple, contact with the top surface of the sample. Strategies against contaminations are well explained as the deposition chambers were gold contaminated.

2.2 The HWCVD for polycrystalline and amorphous material

Synthesis of poly crystalline and amorphous silicon films were performed using the three spherical chamber HWCVD apparatus placed in an arrangement of isosceles triangle shape with one common load lock chamber shown in figure 2.2. Sample can be transferred from one chamber to another without breaking the vacuum. During sample transfer vacuum pressure can be maintained 2×10^{-6} mbar.

This makes the instrument very useful for continuous growth of device fabrication shown in figure 2.1. The spherical shapes for reaction chamber are specially chosen to reduce the internal surface area for a given volume [1].

Figure 2.1 Block diagram of i-p device structure fabricated using HWCVD without breaking the vacuum with the help of sample transfer mechanism.

Figure 2.2 Block diagram of top view of three chamber HWCVD cluster tool for synthesis of polycrystalline and amorphous silicon film.

2.2.1 Growth condition

Silicon films are synthesized using silane (SiH_4) gas. SiH_4 is dissociated into SiH_3 , SiH_2 , SiH and related species using gas discharge (plasma enhanced chemical vapour deposition (PECVD)) or thermal excitation (hot wire chemical vapour deposition (HWCVD)). Atomic hydrogen is produced during the above process. Additional hydrogen is used to control the quality of growth. In addition to deposition, atomic hydrogen can react with silicon and cause etching. Some hydrogen is also incorporated in the growing film depending on the temperature of the substrate. One can get a large variety of silicon films by controlling the growth parameters. These may vary from amorphous silicon using concentrated silane at substrate temperature 200°C , micro crystalline / nano crystalline silicon using hydrogen

diluted silane at 200°C, to polycrystalline silicon using concentrated silane at higher substrate temperature about 600°C.

Synthesis of silicon films is done under optimal growth condition, which means adjusting the available parameters those are critical for the synthesis of the silicon film. In our case chamber pressure, substrate temperature, filament temperature, silane to hydrogen ratio, gas flow rate were taken into consideration. Few other parameters such as the distance between substrate and the filament, filament arrangement and gas flow shower were fixed during the design of the HWCVD instrument shown in figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3 Schematic of HWCVD chamber used for growth of polycrystalline and amorphous silicon film.

All growth experiments for thin film synthesis were performed in the HWCVD system having base pressure of no higher than 1×10^{-6} mbar. Process pressure was maintained between 1×10^{-1} mbar to 6×10^{-2} mbar. A throttle valve at the exit controls the reactor pressure by changing the volumetric flow rate of the gases leaving the reactor. A mixture of pure SiH_4 and pure H_2 was used as process gas for intrinsic silicon film. Diborane (5% diborane, 95% hydrogen) gas was introduced as a source of boron for p-type silicon film. Single filament of tungsten wire, 65 cm long and 0.5 mm diameter wound in a zigzag shape

was resistively heated to 1900°C using a dc power supply. The filament is placed at about 5cm height from the substrate. The area covered by the filament is about 9 cm × 9 cm. The hot filament radiatively heats the substrate to 200°C as measured with a thermocouple placed below the substrate holder. Higher substrate temperature was achieved by a resistive heater placed in contact with the substrate holder from below. A moveable shutter between the wire and the substrate allows several growth steps to be performed under selected gas composition, substrate temperature and filament temperature. This also provides a definite starting and ending point for each step during the growth of the film.

2.2.2 Mechanism of growth of silicon film

The basic steps for silicon film deposition are: dissociation of the reaction gases into precursors on the surface of the hot wire, transportation of precursors to substrate, and diffusion / deposition of the dissociated useful particle species on the surface of the substrate to grow the film. The main factors of the first sub-processes are filament temperature, growth pressure, gas flow rates and substrate temperature. Reaction rate increases with an increase in these factors as evident in published papers [2]. The second sub-processes depend upon the silane to hydrogen ratio and pressure of the reaction gas. If the pressure is higher, the possibility of secondary reactions become higher, and the structure of the deposited film will be inferior. The distance between filament and substrate allows the substrate to be radiatively heated to about 200°C. The substrate temperature can be raised further by additional heating with substrate heater kept below the substrate holder. A closer arrangement will increase the substrate temperature additionally with the substrate heater from the bottom. This will affect the low temperature (below 200°C substrate temperature) growth condition. A higher substrate temperature results in higher mobility of the atoms (Si, H) and causes a relaxation of the structure; thereby resulting in a better quality film [3]. We have used glass substrates during several growth processes which limit the substrate temperature to 600°C though the system was designed to reach 800°C substrate temperature.

2.2.3 Challenges with Hotwire CVD

The main challenges that concern Hotwire CVD are i) uniform film deposition over large substrates (2-4 inch diameter wafer) ii) changes in the properties of the filament as it

ages and spaced in a zigzag pattern iii) chamber pressure limits the possible hydrogen dilution. Uniformity has been addressed in commercial hotwire CVD equipment by modifying filament geometry, gas shower geometry and in some cases by rotating the substrate. Several researchers have found tantalum [4] to be a better filament material than tungsten [5] with lower temperature around 1650 °C. In our case we have kept filament temperature 1900°C.

Chamber pressure can be controlled with mechanical pump and throttle valve. Still maximum hydrogen dilution was 20 sccm which leads to 1.1×10^{-1} mbar of growth chamber pressure. In some stage of growth process we have to reduce the hydrogen dilution to keep the chamber pressure constant. Lower hydrogen dilution leads to more broken and dangling bonds. This will degrade the material quality of the film [6]. We have introduced a hydrogen passivation stage after the growth to overcome this problem.

2.2.4 Calibration of substrate temperature

The temperature of the substrate was determined in situ using a type K (Chromel-Alumel) thermocouple in contact with the top of substrate. Temperature profile of substrate is shown in figure 2.4 under various conditions.

Figure 2.4: Measured substrate temperature versus set substrate heater temperature profile using K-type (Chromel-Alumel) thermocouple.

With filament cold and gas flowing, the substrate temperature increased linearly with the substrate heater setting (curve 'a' in Fig 2.4). With filament hot at $\sim 1900^\circ\text{C}$ and gas

flow, the substrate temperature increased maximum 550°C. It is clear that the substrate heater set temperature is much higher than the actual temperature of substrate.

This may be because the thermocouple reading the substrate heater temperature is near the heater below the substrate holder and far from the substrate. During the above calibration, we keep the tip of a sheathed thermocouple tip touching a dummy 2 inch diameter silicon wafer, kept on the substrate holder, which is used to hold the smaller (1cm×2cm) glass substrate used for the growth. The calibration helps us to evaluate the actual substrate temperature which was crucial for our study as we have used glass as substrate.

2.2.5 Calibration of chamber pressure

We performed the calibration of chamber pressure keeping one sccm continuous silane flow with changing the hydrogen flow ranging from 1 to 75 sccm.

Figure 2.5: Intrinsic silicon growth chamber pressure versus gas (1sccm Silane with H₂) flow plot for the calibration of maximum possible hydrogen dilution.

The corresponding chamber pressure versus gas flow is plotted in figure 2.5. We have to maintain maximum 20 sccm hydrogen flow during growth to maintain the maximum growth pressure under 1.2×10^{-1} mbar.

In some stage of our growth we had to reduce the hydrogen flow to maintain the chamber pressure constant which affected the material quality.

2.3 The HWCVD system for n-type microcrystalline silicon

For phosphorous doped n-type silicon film we have used automated four chamber HWCVD cluster tool with one load lock chamber [7,8]. In this system, samples can be loaded and transferred between chambers using a computerized robotic hand without breaking the vacuum. The chambers were cylindrical and operated in a tantalum filament at lower temperature (1650°C). Microcrystalline n-type phosphorous doped silicon film was deposited on glass and FTO coated glass substrate using this system. A schematic diagram of the growth chamber is shown in Fig 2.6. Organization of the filament and substrate assembly is different than we explained in earlier three chamber HWCVD. Here the substrate was placed upside down on the top of the tantalum filament assembly where the gas flow shower was placed at the bottom of the chamber below the tantalum filament.

2.3.1 Growth conditions

Figure 2.6 Schematic of HWCVD chamber used for deposition of microcrystalline phosphorous doped n-type silicon film.

Thin phosphorous doped microcrystalline silicon film deposited at 350°C substrate temperature with a filament temperature 1650°C for 45 minutes. Base pressure was 1×10^{-6}

mbar while process pressure was maintained at 6.6×10^{-2} mbar. The microcrystalline silicon films were grown at a gas flow ratio of $\text{SiH}_4:\text{H}_2:\text{PH}_3 = 2:50:1$ sccm.

2.4 Discussion

HWCVD is an interesting technique for the low-temperature growth of thin-film silicon. It offers efficient use of high deposition rates, and high hydrogen passivation of defects. The choice of filament and its temperature are critical to the determination of the deposition environment and appropriate precautions must be taken in order to achieve high quality, contamination-free films. For the deposition regime of interest, low-temperature epitaxial growth, tungsten was the most reliable catalyst filament. Tungsten offers a large process window for silicon films with high hydrogen dilution.

Chapter 7

HIT structured n-i-p diode

7.1 Introduction

In this chapter we have reported the fabrication process of n-i-p hetero junction with intrinsic silicon thin layer (HIT) structure diode on fluorine tin oxide coated alkali free borosilicate glass substrate using hot wire chemical vapour deposition (HWCVD) technique. We have grown the complete device structure including i) n type microcrystalline silicon layer on FTO coated glass, ii) intrinsic polycrystalline silicon one micron thick layer, iii) hydrogenated amorphous intrinsic silicon layer (a-Si:H) nearly 5 nm thick, and iv) p type a-Si:H layer at the top. We have measured the dark I-V and the illuminated I-V to observe photo response under visible light. Capacitance measurement was performed to evaluate depletion width, carrier concentration near the depletion region.

7.2 Device structure of n-i-p diode

7.2.1 Device structure

3D and 2D structural schematic diagram of n-i-p diodes fabricated is shown in figure 7.1.

Figure 7.1: 3D and 2D block diagram of HIT structured n-i-p diode

7.2.2 Working principle of the device

In this section we have discussed the operation of n-i-p device along with the band diagram.

7.2.2.1 Schematic device diagram

Well known HIT structure solar cell which combines amorphous silicon and crystalline silicon [1] has been used as guide for our device structure. In our study, we replace the crystalline silicon substrate with intrinsic polycrystalline silicon layer as the base absorber. Highly doped n-type microcrystalline silicon is used as the back contact layer to the base.

Figure 7.2: Schematic diagram of the operation of n-i-p diode fabricated using HWCVD on FTO coated glass substrate.

Thin (about 5 nm) intrinsic hydrogenated amorphous silicon film is grown on top of the intrinsic polycrystalline to form passivating hetero junction. The top emitter layer is p-type hydrogenated amorphous silicon film as shown in figure 7.1. This combination of thin amorphous silicon layers also acts as good surface passivators [2,3,4].

Absorption of high energy photon and resulting electron hole pair generation occurs in the absorber layer. Separation of electrons and holes occurs due to the internal electric field across the intrinsic absorber region, holes move towards p-type silicon layers and electron move towards n-type silicon layer. The strength of internal electric field depends on the doping concentration of the emitter layer. The higher doping concentration of emitter layer (amorphous p-type silicon film) also allows good ohmic contact with the external metal contact.

7.2.2.2 Schematic band diagram

A schematic of equilibrium band diagram of the device is shown in figure 7.3. The parameters used in drawing this diagram, are given in table 7.1.

Figure 7.3: Schematic equilibrium band diagram of n-i-p diode fabricated using HWCVD on FTO coated glass substrate.

The a-Si:H has larger band gap than c-Si base, which causes discontinuities in conduction and valence bands at the heterojunction. Thus it acts as a window layer for light as well as passivates the emitter surface. There is larger band discontinuity in the valence band (0.45 eV) than in the conduction band (0.15 eV). A theoretical simulation indicated that a high discontinuity in the conduction band at the p/i interface prevents electron back diffusion from the absorber layer to the emitter layer and thus reducing loss of minority carriers at the p-type layer [5]. However in the a-Si-c-Si hetero structure, the conduction band discontinuity is small (~0.15eV); hence the structure is not ideal.

Table 7.1: Parameters used for schematic band diagram [6].

Name	Work function	Reference
FTO	$\phi = 4.4 \text{ eV}$	[7]
n-Si:H	$\phi = 4.05 + 0.2$ [Electron affinity of n-Si + $(E_C - E_F)$ (n-Si)] = 4.25 eV, where $E_C - E_F = kT \ln(N_C/N_d)$ with $N_C = 2.8 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $N_d = \sim 1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$	[8]
E_g (c-Si) E_g (a-Si:H) ΔE_g (a-Si:H/c-Si) ΔE_C (a-Si:H/c-Si) ΔE_V (a-Si:H/c-Si)	= 1.1 eV = 1.7 eV = 0.6 eV = 0.15 eV = 0.45 eV	
p-a-Si:H	$E_C - E_F = E_g$ (a-Si) 1.7eV - $(E_F - E_V)$, [$E_F - E_V = 0.35\text{eV}$] = 1.7eV - 0.35eV = 1.35eV $\phi =$ Electron affinity of a-Si + $(E_C - E_F)$ = 3.9 + 1.35 = 5.25 eV	
Aluminium	$\phi = 4.08 \text{ eV}$	

7.2.2.3 Role of passivation and emitter layer

The primary function of a passivation layer in a hetero junction is to reduce the defect density at the interface with the absorber layer (which reduces the interface recombination) while admitting a maximum amount of light to the absorber layer [10]. Hydrogenated intrinsic amorphous layer has wider band gap (about 1.7 eV) and is known to passivate the surface of crystalline silicon [8]. Further, its thickness is about 5 nm, so that it allows light to pass without significant loss. We have grown 5 nm thick amorphous buffer layer using $\text{H}_2:\text{SiH}_4=20:1$ shown in section 4.3.5, chapter 4. This optimized $\text{H}_2:\text{SiH}_4$ ratio allows growing well passivated silicon film [11]. The p type a-Si:H provides the counter doped layer to form the p-i-n diode for photovoltaic action.

7.2.2.4 Role of absorber layer

We have grown one micron thick polycrystalline intrinsic silicon layer used as light absorbing material in our study. As a candidate for light absorbing material this layer has to be sufficiently textured. When the film is around 4-5 micron thick, the surface texture is suitable for light trapping. Film with thickness less than 1.5 micron does not allow necessary surface texturing for light trapping [12,13,14,15]. Optical reflection, transmission and absorption analysis was performed in the section 4.4.8,9,10, chapter 4. Reflectivity is found to be more or less 25% for the absorber layer (intrinsic poly silicon film). This can be further reduced by using a textured back surface. Well passivated absorber layer also prevents recombination of charge carrier before reaching the contacts, improving the device performance.

7.2.3 Front and back contacts

For contact materials we have used fluorinated tin oxide ($\text{SnO}_2:\text{F}$) as back contact with n-type silicon and aluminium (Al) as front contact to p-type amorphous silicon. There are some conditions that the electrode material has to fulfil [16]. The metal contact to p- a-SiH should have high optical transmission (85%) in the entire visible wavelength region where the photovoltaic absorber layers are active. Also to have a well conducting layer the metal contact should have low sheet resistance (10 ohm/square) to minimise series resistance losses with the p and n type layers. A rough surface can be used to increase the optical path of the light by scattering, while the morphology should avoid shunting paths, pinholes or local depletion.

In the case of an ohmic contact with top p-type silicon, the work function of metal needs to be larger or close to the sum of electron affinity and energy gap of p-type semiconductor. In the case of an ohmic contact with bottom FTO, the work function of FTO needs to be smaller or close to the sum of electron affinity and energy gap of n-type semiconductor. In this sense, it would be better to use metal such as gold which has work function about 5 eV [6,9] for the top contact. We have instead used Al which has work function of about 4.2 eV [9], which is not a good choice. This needs to be changed in future trials. We have considered the FTO work function 4.4 eV [7]. If our FTO layer has this work function, it will act as ohmic contact to the bottom n type Si layer. If however, the FTO work function increases during the deposition of silicon layers when subjected to high temperatures, the quality of back contact may degrade [7]. This needs to be checked in future trials.

7.3 Fabrication of n-i-p structure diode

7.3.1 Substrate Preparation

FTO coated alkali free borosilicate glass was used as substrate for n-i-p structured diode fabrication. The substrate was dipped in 2 % hydrofluoric acid (HF) for 5 sec for cleaning followed by nitrogen blow drying before loading in HWCVD reaction chamber. We have also used n-type silicon wafer oxidized to 500 nm silicon dioxide layer as a reference substrate.

7.3.2 Fabrication of n-type layer

Thin 150 nm of phosphorous doped microcrystalline silicon layer was deposited at 350°C substrate temperature with tantalum filament temperature 1650°C for 32 minutes. Base pressure was 1×10^{-6} mbar while process pressure was maintained at 6.6×10^{-2} mbar. The microcrystalline silicon films were grown at a gas flow ratio of $\text{SiH}_4:\text{H}_2:\text{PH}_3 = 2:50:1$ sccm to achieve 150 nm thick film.

After this, the sample was transferred to another HWCVD deposition chamber for growing the rest of the structure. This transfer may affect the performance of the device though we have taken necessary precaution not to add any contamination during the transfer process. For making separate devices, a stainless steel mask was used for deposition of the 3 layers above the n type microcrystalline silicon layer. Hard stainless steel 3 mm × 3mm mask was used to separate all the devices with a 1 mm separation where in one run we can have 18 devices over a 1 cm × 2 cm substrate area.

7.3.3 Growth of intrinsic poly silicon film

Intrinsic poly crystalline silicon film was grown on top of 150 nm n-type silicon film. Thin 20 nm nucleation layers were grown at 400°C substrate temperature with filament temperature 1900°C along a gas ratio of $\text{SiH}_4:\text{H}_2 = 1:20$ for 100 sec. In order to grow thick silicon film, a mixture of SiH_4 and H_2 were used as process gas with a ratio of $\text{SiH}_4:\text{H}_2=5:15$ for 20 min [17]. The growth was performed in a ramp run where silane concentration increased gradually from 1 sccm to 5 sccm in four stages shown in table 7.2 steps 2 to 6. In stages 4 to 6, H_2 gas flow was reduced to keep process pressure constant. We have annealed the silicon film at this stage under 20 sccm of H_2 flow for 30 min followed by a H_2 soaking during cooling the sample from growth temperature to a lower temperature of 200°C for another 50 min.

7.3.4 Fabrication of passivating layer

A thin 5 nm layer of amorphous intrinsic poly silicon films were grown at this 200°C for 15 sec using a gas ratio of $\text{SiH}_4:\text{H}_2=1:20$. This layer acts as a passivating interface layer between the polycrystalline silicon and amorphous silicon emitter (with reference to chapter 4, section 4.3.5).

7.3.5 Fabrication of p-type layer

Amorphous p-type silicon film was grown on top of amorphous intrinsic thin silicon layer. Amorphous boron doped p-type 10 nm thin silicon layer was grown at 200°C substrate temperature with filament temperature 1900°C for 50 sec. The gas flow for this thickness were kept at a ratio of $\text{SiH}_4 : \text{H}_2 : \text{B}_2\text{H}_6 = 1:20:2.2$ sccm. Process pressure was kept in between 1.2×10^{-1} mbar to 1.3×10^{-1} mbar. Hard stainless steel 3 mm \times 3mm mask was used to separate all the devices with a 1 mm separation where in one run we can have 18 devices over a 1 cm \times 2 cm substrate area.

7.3.6 Process flow chart of the device

Figure 7.4: Process flow chart for n-i-p structure device fabrication.

7.3.7 Front and back contact

To form back contact, silicon needed to be removed so bottom fluorine tin oxide (FTO) is exposed. We have used chemical etching under fume hood to etch one micron of silicon from FTO coated glass. Details of chemical etching procedure are explained in Appendix II. Etching of silicon layer was confirmed by measuring the conductivity of FTO. For front contact we have used Aluminium (Al) thermal evaporator with a stainless steel mask containing 1 mm diameter circular exposed area which also aligned with the mask that used for the fabrication of the device. This way thin 100 nm Al film was deposited as top contact. We have used indium between tungsten probe and the Al film to avoid pin hole during I-V measurement as a safety precaution.

Table 7.2: Growth parameter of n-i-p hetero junction diode fabrication process using HWCVD on FTO coated glass substrate. (Sample 99_n-i-p_dev)

Step	Process gas pressure mbar	Substrate heater temp. °C	Filament temp. °C	Gas flow ratio sccm	Duration	Thickness nm	Growth Rate A°/Sec
1	6.6×10^{-2}	350	1650	SiH ₄ :PH ₃ :H ₂ =2:1:50	32 min	180	1
2	6.7×10^{-2}	400	1896	SiH ₄ :H ₂ =1:20	100 sec	20	2
3	7.3×10^{-2}	700	1886	SiH ₄ :H ₂ =1.5:20	100 sec		—
4	6.4×10^{-2}	700	1906	SiH ₄ :H ₂ =2:18	100 sec	214	7
5	6.7×10^{-2}	700	1908	SiH ₄ :H ₂ =3:17	100 sec		—
6	7.1×10^{-2}	700	1906	SiH ₄ :H ₂ =5:15	20 min	805	7
7	5.5×10^{-2}	600	1898	H ₂ =20	30 min	Passivation	—
8	5.6×10^{-2}	600 to 200	1892	H ₂ =20	50 min	Cooling	—
9	6.7×10^{-2}	200	1886	SiH ₄ :H ₂ =1:20	15 sec	5	2
10	1.2×10^{-2}	200	1868	SiH ₄ :B ₂ H ₆ :H ₂ =1:2.2:20	50 sec	10	2

7.4 Results

Results presented in this section are concerned with the electrical characterization of n-i-p diode. We have measured dark and one sun illuminated I-V curve for evaluating the photovoltaic performance of the device. We have also taken capacitance measurement under various bias voltages.

7.4.1 Study of dark and illuminated I-V

Figure 7.5: Dark and illuminated I-V curve of 99 n-i-p diode with square device 100 n-i-p diode with circular device

Dark (a) and illuminated (b) I-V curves for two devices are shown in Fig 7.5. Although diode like behaviour of the device is observed, the effect of shining light is rather small. In particular, the device does not develop any photovoltage. The effect of light is seen as only a small enhancement of current above the dark current like in a photoconductor. One possibility for the absence of photovoltage is that the region near the junction between the intrinsic silicon layer and a-Si:H / p-type a-Si:H layer is of poor quality and full of defects. This region, which is supposed to separate the photo-generated excess electrons and holes to develop the photovoltage, instead acts as a giant excess carrier killer by recombination such that no separation of electrons and holes occurs. The small enhancement of current under light is likely due to reduction in the resistance of the intrinsic silicon film.

From the dark forward bias I-V, the series resistance is as estimated about 1×10^5 ohm. The small reduction of this dark resistance, as seen from the enhancement of current in lighted I-V, suggests need to further improve the quality of the intrinsic silicon film in the device structure .

The leakage current in both devices are not that significant but on illumination of one sun, photo response is very small. This is related to the intrinsic polycrystalline silicon (light absorber) layer which is only one micron thick. Increase in the thickness of absorber layer will improve the photo response under illumination of visible light. Another possible reason is the top portions of the devices are covered by the Al (work function 4.08 eV) dots, (In our case the devices are 9 mm^2 , where the areas covered by the Al dots are 0.8 mm^2) perhaps we should have used gold with higher work function (5.1 eV) to reduce the contact resistance.

7.4.2 Study of capacitance

We have measured capacitance for various bias voltage using Agilent 4284A (20Hz to 2MHz) precision LRC meter.

Figure 7.6: Capacitance ($1/C^2$) versus bias voltage curve of n-i-p structure diode.

The C-V measurement is done to determine the width of the space charge region at zero bias and to obtain unintentional doping concentration in the intrinsic region from the slope of $1/C^2$ versus V (reverse bias) plots shown in Fig 7.6. The capacitance is determined by superimposing a small ac voltage of frequency 555 Hz on the dc bias voltage.

Table 7.3: Estimation of depletion width and majority carrier concentration from capacitance measurement for n-i-p structure diode.

Sample name	Capacitance at zero bias (F)	Device area (cm ²)	Depletion width (nm)	Slope of $1/C^2$ -V curve (F ⁻² -V ⁻¹)	Majority carrier concentration (atom-cm ⁻³)
99_Dev_8	435×10^{-12}	0.09	847	2.3×10^{19}	2×10^{13}
99_Dev_10	776×10^{-12}	0.09	1200	4×10^{18}	3×10^{14}

Table 7.3 lists the capacitance at zero bias, calculated values of depletion width at zero bias and doping concentration, as detailed in section 3.9.4, chapter 3. The measured doping of the intrinsic layer is possibly slightly p-type since the intrinsic layer is grown in the chamber used for growing boron doped silicon.

7.5 Discussion

We have described the fabrication of n-i-p structured hetero-junction device synthesized by HWCVD. The dark I-V characteristics were diode like. However, the light I-V characteristics showed poor photo response, with practically no photo voltage and small photoconductivity. One possible weak link was transfer of sample after deposition of n type layer in one laboratory to another laboratory for completing the synthesis of intrinsic and p-type layers. An attempt was made to fabricate a device with thicker absorber layer. But in this case, the film got lifted due to high tensile stress. So, even though we tried to initially optimize individual layers before attempting synthesis of the final device structure n-i-p, it was insufficient to provide a workable photovoltaic device. For improving the device quality, further optimization of composite structure including the quality of the film and interfaces would be necessary.

Chapter 8

Conclusions and Future Work

8.1 Conclusion

We have demonstrated the viability of growing oriented polycrystalline intrinsic silicon film on several low cost substrates like glass, nickel, TiO₂, sapphire and Si/SiO₂ maintaining a low growth temperature. For application as absorber layer in photovoltaic device, it was envisaged that the film should be polycrystalline with grains as large as possible even if the substrate is amorphous such as glass or Si/SiO₂. Further oriented growth was considered desirable for minimizing grain boundary defects. In order to achieve these objectives, we divided the growth process into three steps. In the first growth step, nucleation of silicon was done at 400°C using dilute mixture of Silane (SiH₄) and hydrogen (H₂). These nuclei had orientation such that they promoted <220> oriented silicon growth on all substrates including glass and Si/SiO₂. An increase in grain size of silicon observed while decreasing the nucleation density (discussed in chapter 4, section 4.4.2) on all five substrates (borosilicate glass, nickel strip, TiO₂ on glass, sapphire and Si/SiO₂) under controlled process pressure of 6.8×10^{-2} mbar with 1 sccm silane in 20 sccm hydrogen. Experimental study with atomic force microscope shows that nucleation density decreases with higher hydrogen dilution (1 sccm silane in 99 sccm hydrogen).

The second step involves the growth of silicon film at 600°C substrate temperature to achieve one micron thick undoped polycrystalline silicon as light absorbing layer for photovoltaic application. In the third step, the grown film is soaked in atomic hydrogen in-situ so as to reduce the number of broken and dangling bonds. This helps to reduce the defects related recombination as well as to improve electrical conductivity.

Resistivity of the as grown undoped silicon films was in the range of 2×10^5 ohm-cm to 2×10^6 ohm-cm with activation energy in the range 0.41 eV to 0.55 eV. As a result of the passivation treatment, we observed photoluminescence as well as photoconductivity response from the undoped silicon films. However, still further improvement is necessary as

the PL spectrum showed defects related luminescence emission extending much below the band gap energy (discussed in chapter 4, section 4.4.11).

From XRD measurements, the silicon films are seen to be preferentially <220> oriented. Transmission electron microscope based cross section image shows a complex structure. The growth following the initial nucleation shows structure which is indicative of mixed twinned epitaxial silicon film in the thickness range 20 nm to 200 nm. Beyond this thickness, the growth is oriented columnar polycrystalline, similar to the observation from XRD. This changeover from nearly epitaxial to polycrystalline structure needs more detailed study.

HWCVD growth of polycrystalline and amorphous boron doped p-type silicon film was performed on several substrates as those used for the undoped silicon films. We have maintained a substrate temperature of 600°C for the growth of polycrystalline and 200°C for amorphous silicon film. Highly conducting, uniform thin boron doped amorphous silicon film was grown on glass substrate in order to use as emitter layer in a photovoltaic device.

We have reported two exploratory experiments to convert undoped silicon films to n-type films. The undoped silicon films deposited on glass were used for these experiments. Both the experiments used continuous wave infrared laser for activating the dopant. In the first experiment, a spin-on phosphorus dopant layer was deposited on the undoped silicon layer. The dopant was driven into the film by point focussed laser irradiation scanning the film surface. In the second experiment, the undoped silicon film was subjected to 100keV phosphorus ion implantation. Again the film was laser annealed for activating the dopant. In both the experiments, we were able to establish the synthesis of doped n-type silicon films as seen from lower resistivity and from phosphorus depth profiling from TOF-SIMS measurement.

However, the morphological structure of films had regions of discontinuity. It is possible that the laser irradiation caused melting of silicon film followed by solidification resulting the observed morphology. There was also loss of the <220> orientation observed in the as-prepared films.

There were extensive trials of control of the laser dose to improve the film morphology. However, better control over the laser beam shape is required for device quality films.

Finally, we prepared n-type conducting polycrystalline silicon films on glass by using another HWCVD system equipped with silane and phosphine, which were used in the device experiment.

An initiative was taken to stack three silicon layers in one structure in the form of an n-i-p diode for photovoltaic application. Here we have followed the well known hetero junction with intrinsic thin layer (HIT) structure. The structure was grown using two different HWCVD systems. Initially n-type silicon film was deposited on ITO coated glass. This was followed by deposition of undoped polycrystalline silicon film and p-type doped amorphous film. The electrical characterization of this n-i-p diode structure was performed under dark and illuminated conditions. Although a diode like I-V characteristics was obtained, the device showed very little photo response. We spent fairly large effort in the synthesis of individual layers used in the device. However, for fabricating the device, we spent only a little effort. It is clear that much more effort is necessary to optimise the steps in the device fabrication. This could involve further improvement in the quality of the layers (preferably depositing all the layers in a single HWCVD system or improved handling in the transfer from one HWCVD system to the other), thicker absorbing base layer, as well better control over deposited thicknesses and junctions between the layers.

8.2 Contribution of this thesis

We have established a three stage process of synthesis of (220) oriented poly-Si films at substrate temperatures below 600°C using HWCVD, facilitating the use of low cost substrates such as glass. The three stages of growth are i) nucleation, ii) thin epitaxial growth and iii) oriented columnar thick growth. Since the rate of growth of silicon film as well as the crystalline fraction of HWCVD films vary with chamber pressure and filament temperature, conditions for depositing poly silicon films of one to two microns thickness have been optimized. In most of our work, one micron thick films were synthesised. We introduced a passivation step in the HWCVD growth of undoped silicon films to reduce the defects. The films were soaked in atomic hydrogen and covered with thin layer of undoped a-Si:H which made them photo-conducting, a basic requirement for photosensitive devices.

Therefore, HWCVD synthesized silicon has the potential of providing base material for low cost photovoltaic cells on low cost glass. We have shown growth of similar material

on a variety of substrates such as TiO₂ on glass, Nickel, sapphire and Si/SiO₂. Films grown on sapphire and Si/SiO₂ could be useful for field effect transistor devices.

For devices we need n-type and p-type silicon layers in combination with the undoped silicon layer. We have presented the conditions for growing by HWCVD p-type polycrystalline as well as a-Si:H layers by adding diborane along with the precursors SiH₄ and H₂. For synthesis of n-type silicon film, we have made exploratory investigations of converting undoped poly silicon films deposited on glass to n-type doped silicon films by using i) phosphorus containing spin-on dopant and by ii) phosphorus ion implantation.

In both cases, low temperature process laser annealing was used: i) to drive the dopant into silicon in the spin-on dopant case and ii) for defect annealing and dopant activation in the ion-implantation case. Formation of large grain low resistivity n-type silicon islands were observed. As such these films were not device quality, the work gives insight into the interaction between laser irradiation and silicon thin film. Apart from the materials synthesis and materials characterization studies, we have done initial experiments with the synthesis of a p-i-n structure based on the investigations. This structure uses HWCVD for the deposition of microcrystalline n-type silicon film on FTO coated glass with 98% hydrogen dilution, followed by growth of undoped polycrystalline silicon and the top layer is combination of undoped a-Si:H and p-type a-Si:H.

8.3 Challenges during the work

We have faced many challenges during the several phases of our research work. Some of them are discussed here.

It was decided that we should work at temperatures below 600°C and try to work out a synthesis technique for growing defect free large grain silicon films. We chose several substrates based on literature survey and accessibility. Silicon on sapphire had been used earlier for silicon films for transistors. Nickel foil was oriented substrate. Of course glass has been visualized as cheap substrate. TiO₂ as selective contact is currently popular and was also known to be oriented as we obtained from Washington Univ. St. Louis, Missouri, USA.

Some practical difficulties were: It was really difficult to cut sapphire and nickel into small pieces. Shape of sapphire substrate was never uniform and nickel strip have a bending at the edge due to the manual blade cutter.

After many trials and investigations, we did not find much improvement in the grain size or orientation in the silicon films grown on other substrate; hence we have selected glass for device growth. Choice of Si/SiO₂ as substrate was a replacement of glass for X-TEM because of cleavage property and for FTIR measurements since glass does not transmit beyond 2.5 microns. In the HWCVD apparatus, there were two chambers, one for growing p-type silicon and the other for growing undoped silicon. It turned out that there was some small leak in the chamber meant for undoped film growth which degraded the undoped film quality. Trials in reducing the leak were partly successful. So, for most of the experiments we have grown undoped silicon in the chamber meant for growing p-type films. As a result, cleaning the chamber was necessary before growth of undoped silicon to avoid unwanted boron doping. The filament of HWCVD was changed before every process run. For that we have to open the chamber followed by cleaning, heating, flashing and dummy run before process. This way to prepare the HWCVD for a process run, it took almost a week.

In addition to these, there is no provision of monitoring the substrate surface temperature in the growth chamber. We carried out calibration of substrate surface temperature under different conditions of filament temperature and substrate heater. Even so, some departure during thin film growth cannot be ruled out.

The biggest challenge was synthesizing n-type doped silicon film. There was no provision for introducing phosphine in our HWCVD apparatus. So, we tried to use undoped silicon film and convert it to n-type as described. The greatest challenge came from annealing. Thermal annealing required temperature greater than 600°C, not desirable for glass substrate. So we tried laser annealing. But found the dissymmetry of irradiation is very uncertain because of the uncertainty of focus. During laser annealing it was difficult to locate the focusing distance of the laser spot as the laser tool was not equipped with a beam profiler. In this case we had to locate the focusing condition allowing the laser to scan on a small part of the silicon film as dummy process run. With practically no other monitoring of the beam, too loose focus did not provide sufficient annealing and tight focussing caused thin silicon to melt and solidify into island, again undesirable.

We would like to mention another difficulty we faced in the optical measurements and their analysis. Optical measurements were always difficult for smaller substrates using the standard instrument. In most cases we had to reduce the beam diameter of light source for the reflection and transmission spectral measurements. That is not difficult by itself. The

difficulty arises in matching the intensity of beams on the reference side and the sample side for both reflectance and transmission measurements. These spectra invariably have interference fringes. By using $T/(1-R)$ obtained from the T and R spectra, it is possible to minimize the interference effect. However cancellation of the interference suffers if there are errors in the absolute magnitudes of T and R determined from experiment, introducing errors in the subsequent analysis. Thus special care is necessary in determining the absolute values of T and R.

8.4 Future work

The successful incorporation of the layers described in this work into an efficient photovoltaic device is, of course, the ultimate goal. The best possible approach would be in future to have a HWCVD cluster tool designed for the fabrication of n-i-p diode without breaking the vacuum. This should help in improving the quality of each layer as well as interfaces between different layers which seem to be of poor quality in our experimental structure. In case a single system for growing the whole device structure is not possible as happened in our case, better methods of handling and transferring samples from one system to another without exposure to atmosphere, by using portable desiccated and sealable chamber, need to be ensured before proceeding for the device work.

First indication of improvement of device will be in its dark I-V characteristics having i) low leakage current and ii) some forward I-V region of diode ideality factor $1 < n < 2$. Secondly, the device should also have a measurable open circuit photovoltage and short circuit current under light irradiation. We will need to know the thickness of each layer. This may be done by growing the layers on Si/SiO₂ substrate, which can be cleaved and a cross sectional TEM image will give the thickness values, and would require optimization. We will also need to check the conductivity of each layer. We could try and use combination of free carrier absorption and in-plane dc conduction measurements for this purpose.

Further improvement may require increase in the thickness of undoped silicon film from one micron to several microns to increase the light absorption. For this, we have to focus on the growth step thickening of layers. On one hand, thick film has to be grown at a reasonable growth rate. At the same time, film should not be excessively stressed which will cause it to lift from the substrate. Film quality should also be sufficiently good for carrier

collection. For this quantum efficiency measurements will be of use. After improvement in the electrical characteristics, loss of light will have to be minimized. This will require anti-reflection coating, and possibly texturization of the substrate. The anti-reflection coating should also serve as efficient current collector.

Regarding the laser irradiation based annealing of films, apart from the control on beam energy, it will be useful to have better control on the focus and have capability to control the shape of the beam, so as to avoid melting of silicon while providing effective diffusion / defect annealing.

Before closing, there is one result of our work which could be of wider significance. While investigating the structure of the silicon film grown on Si/SiO₂ by using X-TEM (Figure 4.4, Chapter 4), we found a region of the grown silicon film (close to the substrate) which was epitaxial or nearly so. This was unexpected since growth is done on SiO₂ which is amorphous. This must have resulted from the initial nuclei getting connected by lateral growth when the substrate temperature was ramped up to 600°C, while the growth rate was still low and was being ramped up. Being a thin region, this part was not observable in the XRD measurements, which showed (220) oriented polycrystalline silicon film. Indeed X-TEM result did show the thick oriented polycrystalline columnar growth as well, seen as (220) oriented polycrystalline film in the XRD measurements. Our above finding came at a very late stage of work, but it will be interesting to explore the conditions responsible for growing epitaxial silicon film on glass more carefully. Furthermore, properties of this material need to be investigated in greater detail and could find application in another device such as field effect transistor.

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